
Tritium Cross Sections

Comparison of tritium cross sections on d, Li-6, and Li-7
(GEANT4 v.10.3 / v.10.2 - TENDL2009 / 2014 - ENDF data)

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8 May 2017

Figura 1

In this study, the interaction cross sections of tritium with deuterium, Lithium-6, and Lithium-7 have been identified, analyzed, and compared. The findings are as follows:

1. We used Geant4 10.3, released on February 28, 2017, modelling the tritium interactions using experimental cross sections (called G4TENDL1.0) derived from the TENDL-2014 [1][2] and ENDF/B-VII.1 [3] databases. Specifically:
 - t + d is described with ENDF/B-VII.1 data.
 - t + Li-6 is described with ENDF/B-VII.1 data.
 - t + Li-7 is described with TENDL-2014 data.

The corresponding cross sections are plotted in Figure 1.

2. We previously [4] used version 10.2 of Geant4, with the cross sections described using parameterized theoretical functions, which are less accurate than the experimental cross sections mentioned above.

Comparisons:

a. $t + d$: Total Cross Section

- a.1. **Page 3**: Comparing the red curves in **Figure 1** and **Figure 2** (the first obtained from GEANT4 and the second directly from the ENDF database), we confirm that the tritium cross section on deuterium in GEANT4 v.10.3 indeed can be derived from ENDF/B-VII.1 data.
- a.2. **Page 3**: Comparing the red curve with the black curve in **Figure 2**, we observe how the tritium cross section on deuterium changes from the data-derived model (red) to the previously used parameterized theoretical model (black).
- a.3. **Page 4**: Comparison between the ENDF/B-VII.1 data curve in **Figure 2** and data previously provided in the literature (**Figure 3**) [5].

b. $t + \text{Li-6}$: Total Cross Section

- b.1. **Page 5**: Comparing the magenta curves in **Figure 1** and **Figure 4** (the first from GEANT4 and the second directly from the ENDF database), we confirm that the tritium cross section on Lithium-6 in GEANT4 10.3 can be derived from ENDF/B-VII.1
- b.2. Comparing the magenta curve with the black curve in **Figure 4**, we observe the change from the data-derived model (magenta) to the previously used parameterized theoretical model (black).

c. $t + \text{Li-7}$: Total Cross Section

- c.1. **Page 6**: Comparing the blue curves in **Figure 1** and **Figure 5** (the first from GEANT4 and the second directly from the TENDL database), we confirm that the tritium cross section on Lithium-7 in GEANT4 10.3 is derived from TENDL-2014 data.
- c.2. Comparing the blue curve with the black curve in **Figure 5**, we observe how the tritium cross section on Lithium-7 changes from the data-derived model (blue) to the previously used parameterized theoretical model (black).

d. $t + \text{Li-7}$: $2n$ and $n+\alpha$ Channels

- d.1. **Page 7**: **Figure 6** compares the cross sections obtained from TENDL-2009 and TENDL-2014 data for two specific interaction channels of tritium on Lithium-7: $2n$ (red) and $n+\alpha$ (green). **Figure 7** shows the corresponding results from the graph belonging to the TENDL-2009 database.

Conclusions from the Comparisons

a. $t + d$: Total Cross Section

- The ENDF/B-VII.1 cross section is fully compatible with previous literature, except in the high-energy region ($E > 3$ MeV).
- The parameterized theoretical function does not adequately describe the experimental data from the ENDF database.

b. $t + \text{Li-6}$: Total Cross Section

- Similar to the $t + d$ case, the parameterized theoretical function does not sufficiently match the experimental data from the ENDF database.

c. $t + \text{Li-7}$: Total Cross Section

- In this case, the parameterized theoretical function describes the experimental data from the TENDL-2014 database quite well.

d. $t + \text{Li-7}$: $2n$ and $n+\alpha$ Channels

- Comparing the $2n$ and $n+\alpha$ cross sections obtained from TENDL-2009 and TENDL-2014 data, we observe that in TENDL-2014, these cross sections begin to show significant values at tritium energies starting from 2 MeV, whereas in the previous database (TENDL-2009), this threshold was 5 MeV.

t + d: Total Cross Section

Figura 1

Figura 2

t + d: Total Cross Section

Figura 2

Figura 3

t + Li6: Total Cross Section

Figura 1

Figura 4

t + Li7: Total Cross Section

Figura 1

Figura 5

t + Li7: Cross Sections (t,2n) and (t,n+α)

Figura 6

Incident triton data / TENDL-2009 / Li7 / / Cross section

Figura 7

References:

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